

Title: Optimisation Algorithm for AI Services

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Nowadays, there is an explosion of artificial intelligence (AI) research in all the fields. Therefore, we can find various 'plug-and-play' pretrained AI models spanning in different domains, including generative AI, language understanding, computer vision, speech, biology and recommender systems [1]. In parallel, there is much effort to benchmark the performance of AI models for different services and in different processing devices [2], [3].

In XGAIN we combine these directions and our scope is to provide an orchestrator that uses this information to propose personalised configuration solutions to users based on their services requirements. In the realm of dimensioning issues, which revolve around identifying the necessary technology for a particular application, a technology selection algorithm assumes a pivotal function. These dimensioning challenges frequently encompass intricate factors, including capacity planning, the allocation of resources and optimization of costs. Given the extensive array of available technologies and choices, the manual determination of the most apt technology for a given situation becomes progressively more demanding and automation is needed, as investigated in XGAIN.

Diverse AI services are applicable in rural areas considering different case studies. An example is drones using detailed colour information to indicate plant health, hence farmers can monitor crops as they grow and any problems can be quickly dealt with. Moreover, cameras are able to detect animals in the farm without physical presentation of the shepherd. Finally, in terms of remote patient monitoring [4], considering eHealth domain that is of utmost importance in remote areas, installed devices, such as CAPTAIN COACH device [5], in people's house could offer services such as the detection of people, their pose and emotion analysis.

These paradigms are inspired by some of XGAIN's Use Cases and show indicative AI services. All these services require specific processing devices to be executed, i.e. to provide their inference. Additionally, these services are of different type and different models are applicable, e.g. object detection and pose detection can be served by yolo [6] and posenet [7] models respectively. It is easy to understand that each model has different performance metrics, e.g. inference latency, memory or power consumption, to different devices, such as Raspberry Pi or NVIDIA's single board computers (SBCs).

The above concepts depict that there are many processing enablers for AI services and different processing models with different performance in these devices. Thus, our algorithm helps to overcome the limitations of manual decision-making, which can be time-consuming, error-prone, and subjective. It leverages computational power to perform complicated calculations and analyse multiple scenarios, resulting in reliable decisions. The inputs of our process are:

- a) User's services among a pool of representative services,
- b) Different processing devices,
- c) Known (based on benchmarking) performance metrics of each service to each device,

- d) User's constraints, such as processing latency limitation.

The output is the allocation of services to specific processing devices satisfying the user's constraints considering the minimisation of an objective such as the total cost of computing devices.

The aforementioned problem has been designed as a mixed integer programming (MIP) problem and Gurobi solver [8] is used. MIP problem is a mathematical optimisation problem, hard to be solved, in which some or all of the variables are restricted to be integers, in our case we have the pairs among the services and processing enablers. The general formulation of an optimisation problem includes the objective and the constraints. The algorithm minimise/maximise the objective satisfying simultaneously the constraints.

Our automated approach, based on optimisation theory, offers straightforward solution to where the users have to be served, i.e. in which device, subject to their constraints and the objective. This described process is not only useful in XGAIN, but it can also be generally applied for scenarios where there is the need of pairing between AI services and processing enablers.

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